

Original Research Article

Examiners' Professional Status and Efficiency of Marking the Cameroon General Certificate of Education Examinations

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Abstract

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This research sought to examine the Effects of examiners' professional status on the efficiency of marking the Cameroon General Certificate of Education examinations. The study was prompted by the wide differences sometimes observed between the marks/scores awarded by a Chief examiner and other examiners over the same scripts marked. The study was carried out in the Republic of Cameroon using the 2021 GCE Examiners of both the Ordinary and Advanced Level general subjects. The sample size of the study was made up of 360 examiners and 36 chief examiners. The descriptive survey research design was used where questionnaire with both close and open ended questions were constructed and validated for data collection. Data were analysed descriptively, thematically and with the use of SPSS statistical package. The findings revealed that the professional status of an examiner influences marking efficiency. Based on the findings, some recommendations were made: The GCE board could organize regular seminars/workshops for examiners; The Conveyor Belt marking system of marking should be used to encourage specialization; Two independent marking of all scripts if not at least for the borderline cases (39-49 for O/L and 34-44 for A/L) could also increase marking efficiency; The selection of examiners should be strictly based on professional backings; and GCE examiners should be more committed and responsible especially during the marking exercise.

Keywords: Examiner, Marking efficiency, Marking, Professional status

INTRODUCTION

Education is a very important tool that enhances change and improvement in the society (Tambo, 2012). This study examines the relationship between Examiners' professional status and the efficiency of marking the Cameroon General Certificate of Education examinations (GCE). Professional status is the degree to which an individual has attained the specialized competence, attitudes and recognition that characterize a profession in general. There are some indications that many teachers see professional status largely in terms of the third

element, recognition. The research is focused on the marking of essay-type examinations, and it makes reference to the traditional method of marking candidates' scripts. As viewed by Tambo (2003 p.207), "assessment or measurement refers to the process of developing, administering and marking (scoring) tests and other assessment instruments". "Assessment is a synonym to measurement". (Hopkins and Stanley, 1981 p. 3). Evaluation on the other hand is the interpretation of the marks or scores produced by the assessment process in

order to make judgement or decisions. The definition above tells us that assessment involves three stages i.e. development of assessment instrument, administration of assessment instrument and marking (scoring) of the assessment instrument. This research is therefore focused on the last stage – the marking (scoring) of assessment instruments. Efficiency generally describes the extent to which time, effort or cost is well utilised for the intended task or purpose. Efficiency is a measurable concept, qualitatively determined by the ratio of output to input or the ratio of the amount of resources (products) produced to the amount of resources consumed. Therefore marking efficiency describes the extent to which time, effort or cost is well utilised for the marking of examinations.

Historically, the educational development of Cameroon saw light after the First World War of 1914 specifically during the period of British Mandate (1922-1946), during which the German colonial system of education ceded place to the British and French colonial systems. With the publication of the Phelps-stokes commission's report in 1922, the British government effected changes in its colonial policy on education with the British Secretary of State appointing an Advisory Committee on Native education in British tropical dependencies. The deliberations of the Advisory Committee led to the publication of the Education policy for British tropical Africa in 1925, which recommended the establishment of schools at all levels - primary, secondary and university together with technical and vocational schools (MacOjong, 2008).

The Advanced Teachers Training College (ENS) was the first and only teacher training college for secondary school teachers which was opened in Yaounde in 1961 with an annex created in Bambili in 1967 (Shu and Tchombe, 2000). Before then, secondary school teachers either came from abroad or were drawn from among those who had previously been specifically trained to teach in primary schools. The London Advanced Level Certificate Examination (GCE Advanced 'Levels) or its equivalence was the qualification for entry into ENS, and the duration of training was two or three years, depending on the student's entry qualification (Tchombe, 2000). On the 10th of August 1979, following Presidential Decree No. 79/309/08/1979 to give ENS some structure and effective functioning, the institution was divided into two cycles, and nine departments. The first cycle operated both in Bambili and Yaounde. The first cycle had three sections and the duration of the courses lasted for two to three years, and four years for those offering the bilingual series. The entry requirements were a pass at the GCE Advanced Level. Its three sections were: Letters (bilingual series and human sciences), Sciences, and Science of Education (MacOjong, 2008). The certificates obtained at the end of these programs of study were: The Diploma for General Secondary Teaching (DIPCEG) and

The Diploma for Assistant Teachers of Training colleges (DIPENIA).

As of today, Yaounde and Bambili operate both first and second cycles with other universities like Maroua and Ngoundere. The universities of Bamenda and Buea also train teachers through their faculties of education and science of education respectively. They also run Higher Technical Teachers' Training colleges (HTTTC).

From inception, GCE examinations were managed by the University of London Schools Examination Board (ULSEB) until 1976. By this time, all examination questions were first set in London and then sent to Cameroon for administration. The scripts were then sent back to London for marking. The London system of marking was such that each subject panel was made up of subject moderators, Chief examiners, Assistant chief Examiners and Assistant examiners. The Chief examiners and Assistant chief examiners proposed questions which were moderated by moderators. Deliberations were usually made between the moderators, Chief examiners and Assistant chief examiners in order to agree on the marking guide. The Assistant examiners were given scripts to take home and mark after which samples of the marked scripts are sent to the moderators and Chief examiners to crosscheck the scoring before grading. Later on, exams were set by Cameroonians and sent to London for vetting and then sent back to Cameroon for administration. Marking started going on in Cameroon by Cameroonians who were trained on the spot by moderators and chief examiners from London, who equally supervised or moderated the marking. This assistance from moderators and chief examiners coming from London went on for some time before the whole marking exercise was left in the hands of Cameroonians under the supervision of the Ministry of National Education.

Therefore, the transition from the University of London Board to the Cameroon GCE Board went through an intermediary organ which was the then Ministry of National Education in Cameroon. The department of examinations in the Ministry of National Education made agreements with the British government and the University of London Examination Board for Cameroonians to be trained in Britain on the management of GCE Examinations. Some selected Cameroonians were then sent to Britain for this training and after their return, the GCE London tradition was handed over to the Ministry of National Education in 1976. Cameroonians like Prof. Lydia Eveny'a Luma and then Hon. Sona Elonge were some of the first Anglophones to head the management of GCE Examinations organized by the Ministry of National Education.

Under the Ministry of National Education, Examiners no longer carried scripts home to mark. There was just one examination centre which was Lycée Bilingue Essos

Yaounde. Examiners invited out of the examination area were paid mission orders. The examiners were provided with accommodation, food and a bus for daily transportation, while examiners were paid a fixed rate for each script, alongside out of station's allowances.

As time went on, the management of GCE examinations under the Ministry of National Education became devastating as it was plagued by numerous irregularities. These included poor translation, poor printing, wrong presentation and pagination, wrong spellings, shortages of question papers and other examination materials, late arrival of question papers at some examination centres, examination leakages, non-respect of published time tables, wrong instructions, delays in publication of results and above all, the use of unqualified examiners to mark the GCE. These management irregularities reached a crisis point particularly given that the Cameroon government had fallen short of honouring her financial obligations to the London GCE Board for technical support such as the printing of GCE Certificates that London had stopped. The government also could not continue paying the dues of the local GCE examiners.

It was against the backdrop of all these irregularities that on the 1st of July 1993 the Presidential Decree No. 93/172 signed by President Paul Biya created the Cameroon GCE Board. Article 3 of the above Decree and the Prime Ministerial Order No. 112/CAB/PM of the 12 of October 1993, signed by Achidi Achu spelt out the duties of the Cameroon GCE Board. The main duties of the Cameroon GCE Board are to organise exams for Ordinary and Advanced Level general subjects, foreign examinations, examinations in English for the award of "Baccalaureate Technique", Brevet de Technicien, "Brevet d'Etudes Professionnelles" and "Brevet Professionnel". Administratively the organigram of the GCE Board begins with the GCE Board Council which is headed by a Chairperson. After the chairperson, the next authority is the Registrar of the GCE Board. Since inception, three Registrars have led the GCE Board till this date of publication. The registrars are appointed by Presidential Decree. The Pioneer registrar Mr. Azong Wara Andrew stayed in office from December 1993 to May 1997, Dr. Omer Weyi Yembe took over from 1997 to 2006 during which a series of training workshops were organized for examiners especially with the introduction of multiple-choice examinations. He was succeeded by Dr. Monono Homphry Ekema from 2006 to 2018 and then Mr Dang Dominic from 2018 till this day of publication.

Contextually, the taking over of the running of GCE examinations from the Ministry of National Education by the Cameroon GCE Board came with lots of innovations. Each subject panel is now made up of an Assessor, a Chief examiner, Assistant chief examiners, Examiners and Assistant examiners for both Ordinary and Advances Level subjects. The assessor oversees the setting,

moderation and marking of GCE examinations, which are all led by the Chief examiner. Marking only usually begins after the discussion of the marking guide and trial marking which are used to boost the professional development of examiners as they get to the marking centres. The Chief Examiner and Assistant Chief Examiners usually pick up marked scripts randomly from each Examiner and remark to check the efficiency of the marking. This at times reveals large mark differences that would cause the Chief examiner to redistribute the scripts of such examiners for remarking. Examiners with little marking experience and those without professional teaching certificates in the most part are usually the ones that have large mark differences with Chief examiners. After the marking or scoring by Examiners and Assistant examiners, they do their individual checking before recording the marks (A-checking). The marked scripts are then handed to the examination secretariat of the GCE board where secretariat workers cross check the addition and marks recorded by the examiners (B-checking). The candidates are graded first by the whole subject panel (Assessor, Chief examiner and Assistant Chief examiners) for pre grading and later on graded together with a GCE board official (final grading). At the end of every marking session all examiners are graded by the whole subject panel. Based on this grading, the GCE board usually drops examiners that do not mark well. The board also pays 200frs and 275frs respectively for each O/L and A/L script marked. Generally the marking in most cases takes a few more days beyond the number of days allocated by the GCE board. Examiners usually mark for eight hours daily, interspersed by a one hour break. At the end of each marking session there is usually a workshop during which papers are presented to improve the marking skills of examiners.

Statement of the Problem

Every candidate who writes an examination expects that he/she is given a deserved mark, no matter who marks the script. The Cameroon government puts in much to ensure the smooth running of GCE examinations. This is done through regular subventions, appointment of officials to the GCE board just to name a few. Despite all these, the researcher a twenty three year experienced GCE examiner and Assistant chief examiner, has come across many issues concerning the marking of the GCE that pricked his imagination. The researcher noticed that the GCE Board regularly sends off and replaces a handful of examiners each year for poor or inefficient marking of scripts and/or poor conduct. He was also disturbed by the fact that a good number of examiners after marking scripts, usually have very alarming differences of about ± 8 marks and above when checked by Chief examiners. The worst of it is when chief

examiners usually redistribute poorly marked scripts of some examiners to other examiners to remark, thus prolonging the marking exercise.

The above circumstances as feared by the researcher could cause the falsification of marks, leading to certificate devaluation, academic inflation and societal degradation. Consequently, the researcher sought to find out the influence of examiners' professional status on the efficiency of marking the Cameroon General Certificate of Education examinations.

Objective of the Study

The main aim of this study was to find out whether examiners' professional status has an influence on the efficiency of marking the GCE examinations.

Research Question

What is the relationship between examiners' professional status and GCE marking efficiency?

Research Hypothesis

Ha: There is a significant relationship between examiners' professional status and GCE marking efficiency.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between examiners' professional status and GCE marking efficiency.

Conceptual Review

Professional status

Byrnes, et al. (2006) see that the need to invest in the quality of teachers is based on the challenges that national governments face with respect to their educational systems. Changes in society have led to new challenges for schools. That extended professionalism and continuous professional development of teachers are emphasized in national and European debates (European Council 2009). This raises the question whether the curricula in Teacher Education prepare teachers to meet those wider expectations.

Typical attributes of a profession According to Snoek, Swennen and Van der Klink (2009) are:

Professional autonomy, through professional monopoly of the members of the profession who have control over their own work; Professionals should have control over the entry requirements into the profession

and the further professional development of the individual members. Professions also have the power to judge, and subsequently even to exclude, members who do not keep to the professional standards and ethical code of that profession; An ethical code as a means to win the trust of the public and public bodies (often governments) that have the power to license the profession and its members; and to serve as a guideline for good conduct of the members of that particular profession and fourthly a strong academic knowledge base, consisting of formal or technical knowledge (Goodson & Hargreaves 1996).'

The professional has an understanding of the complexity of the world and of knowledge, and consequently of the work he does. He does not hesitate to bring in experts from other fields. He does not hesitate to say 'I do not know'. The person who has a ready answer for every question is a faker. (Journal of Cooperative Extension, 1967).

According to Evetts (2009) and Koster (2002), a Profession is a distinct category of occupational work; Professionalisation is a process in which a professional group pursues, develops, acquires and maintains more characteristics of a profession while Professionalism is the conduct, demeanour and standards which guide the work of professionals.

Gewirtz et al (2009) assert that the changing context of schools asks for a change in qualities expected from professionals (new professionalism), with a focus on effectivity, accountability, national safeguarding and control; A strong focus on the quality of work and a stronger emphasis on output requirements; Public accountability, where teachers have to explicate how their teaching contributes to achieving the intended learning outcomes and the implementation of standards describing competences and qualifications of beginners and expert members of professions.

As observed by Freidson (2001, p.12):

"An organized occupation gains the power to determine who is qualified to perform a defined set of tasks, to prevent all others from performing that task and to control the criteria by which to evaluate performance. The organized occupation creates the circumstances under which its members are free of control by those who employ them."

From an ethical standpoint, Skrtic (1991, p. 87), asserts that:

'Professions are given greater autonomy than other social groups. They set their own standards, regulate entry into their own ranks, discipline their members, and operate with fewer restraints than the arts, trades or businesses. In return they are expected to serve the

public good and enforce high standards of conduct and discipline’.

In the eyes of Nooteboom (2006), the theories on trust show the importance of competence, integrity and dedication of the members of a profession to gain the trust of the public and the state and to justify the professional mandate. The members of a profession have a large responsibility to live up to those expectations with respect to competence, integrity and dedication. This is both a responsibility of individual members of the profession and of the professional community as a whole. Nooteboom also feels that trust in dedication of the professional is closely connected to empathy of professionals for their clients.

Elements that contribute to the professionalism of teachers as observed by Marco and Hogeschool (2009) are knowledge, skills and attitudes.

Professional Status and Marking Efficiency

It has long been established that when marking public examinations in the UK, inter-marker agreement is imperfect, varying significantly among examination subjects as well as among teams of markers (Suto & Nadas, 2008; Baird & Morrissey, 2002; Laming, 2004).

Filer and Pollard (2000) identify that unreliable and/or aberrant marking directly affect the ‘legitimacy’ of systems of assessment. The concept of ‘legitimacy’ is crucial as the outcomes of assessment can mean economic and social rewards for some, reduced access to educational and occupational opportunities for others.

Suto and Nadas also view that once examiners have been selected, both good practice and statutory regulation dictates that training should be provided in the correct marking practice for the award/qualification to be examined.

The Qualifications and Curriculum Authority (QCA) stipulated in their review of question paper setting and senior examiner training, for GCSE and A levels (2008), that those responsible for training examiners:

“Identify training needs for individuals and groups, organise examiner training programmes and produce centralised training and guidance materials” (p. 9).

QCA also states that although training of examiners is an important factor in the quality control process and that training can also improve the consistency of examiners’ individual marking (intra-rater reliability)”, it should not be used as a standalone management control. Training can bring examiners’ differences in leniency (inter-rater reliability) to an acceptable level but it cannot eliminate them. It is obviously a sensible approach to train new examiners so they are fully aware of their duties e.g. how

to annotate scripts and where they should award marks (based on Blooms taxonomy level descriptors, partial responses provided etc). This training may depend on whether they are: First-time examiners, who need training on all aspects of the examining process relevant to their role before marking items; new to the awarding body and require training specific to the awarding body’s procedures; and new to the particular unit/component or specification and require training specific to that unit/component or specification.

The QCA also requires that during examiners’ first marking period, and on subsequent occasions, if necessary, they should be allocated a mentor, normally a more senior examiner e.g. a team leader, to provide close support throughout the marking period.

According to Mathew (2009), a training workshop for examiners is where they gain a greater understanding of the organisation, some background training on assessment procedures e.g. where and how to annotate scripts, meanings of command words (based on Bloom’s taxonomy) etc.

Mthembu (2014) is of the opinion that, there are various factors which have been identified by various scholars as likely to contribute to the accuracy of marking. These factors include the general knowledge and the level of education of the marker, subject knowledge, personality and work ethics, teaching and marking experience as well as training provided. Experienced Markers and Senior Markers must be placed in application, synthesis, analysis, and evaluation questions. Such questions are more challenging and need markers who are dynamic with the ability to interpret candidates’ responses correctly using the marking guidelines.

Wiseman (1949) recommends General impression marking, as an approach which could accelerate multiple marking to the point where it offered a viable alternative to single marking completed analytically: Marking by general impression is a much quicker (and, therefore, cheaper) process than marking analytically.

The Task of Marking Public Examinations

According to Mthembu (2014) the task of marking public examinations is different from the day to day marking of schoolwork. This is a process that includes a variety of factors. It also entails the movement of examination scripts from one marking team to another (question marking model), from the Marker to the Moderator (Senior Marker, Deputy Chief, Chief Marker and Internal Moderator). Unlike the day to day marking at school, the marking of public examinations involves the checking of scripts by the Examination Assistants as well. In other words, the marking of public examinations differs from School Based marking because it has various levels of

quality assurance designed to ensure that no candidate is unfairly advantaged or unfairly disadvantaged (Mthembu, 2014). He also holds that the marking of candidates' work in public examinations is one of the most challenging but rewarding exercises.

Marking Schemes

Hounsell (2014) maintains that the most important aspect of good and accurate marking is the Marker's familiarisation with the marking scheme/guidelines. Desforges (1989) views that mark schemes are fundamentally used by examiners to guide and inform their decisions throughout the examination process, however, like all documents, marking schemes are open to interpretation.

In order to aid reliability of the marking process, the Qualification and Curriculum Authority, QCA (2008), General Certificate of Secondary Education (GCSE) and General Certificate of Education (GCE) code of practice suggest that mark schemes should:

- Be clear and designed so that they can be easily and consistently applied;

- Include general instructions on marking;

- Allocate marks commensurate with the demands of questions/tasks;

- Include the mark allocation for each question/task and part of a question/sub-task, with a more detailed breakdown where necessary;

- Include marking instructions for those questions where extended written answers are expected and the quality of written communication used by candidates will be assessed;

- Include an indication of the nature and range of responses, appropriate to the subject, likely to be worthy of credit;

- State the acceptable responses to each question/task, or part thereof, with detail that allows marking in a standardised manner; and

- Allocate credit for what candidates know, understand and can do.

The marking schemes for any particular examination should obviously be highly specific to it. For instance, it would be adequate for an examiner to decide to 'award the mark of 1 for each significant point' and he would have to make clear what the significant points are. As Thyne (1974, p.248) suggests that: "The more precisely the relevant performances are described in the marking scheme, the more relevant and consistent the marking is likely to be".

Marking Models or Approaches

The following marking approaches could be used when

marking examinations (Leaning to Teach, Teaching to Learn, 2014):

Marking per question or Item level marking where the examiner marks each question separately in all the scripts. This makes the preparation for marking to be easier.

Marking per section in which case the examiner marks each section separately in all the scripts. It increases the speed of marking.

The "whole script marking" model which requires the examiner to mark all questions and sections in each script alone. Good for very experienced examiners with high content and professional background.

Single marking where a single examiner marks a candidate's script once and gives the final score. May not be a very reliable approach.

Double marking in which case two examiners mark a candidate's script and the average of the scores is awarded to the candidate. This ensures accuracy.

Multiple marking where more than two examiners mark a candidate's script and the average score becomes the candidate's final mark. It is a more accurate and reliable approach.

Systems of Marking

Ngara and Ngara (2012) identify three broad marking systems being used in developing countries:

Traditional Marking System

Here several envelopes of scripts are given to one examiner to mark. One examiner marks all the questions attempted by the candidates in each script. A percentage of the scripts marked (about 10%) by each examiner are crossed marked by a team leader to check examiners marking. This is done at several stages of the marking exercise to ensure reliability and consistency. Where deviations are more than + or - 2 on the total score, the examiner is requested to remark the scripts or responses to certain questions and the additions are checked.

Conveyor Belt Marking System

In this system several markers successively mark a script with each marker specialising in marking particular questions or sections. Marking teams are formed in which the team leader keeps all the scripts and mark sheets issued out to each examiner and ensures that marks are correctly entered.

Figure 1. Nine Steps of the Marking Process
Source: Adopted from Ofqual (2013)

Onscreen Marking

This is a marking system that uses an ePEN to mark candidates' scripts.

Marking Methods

Analytical or point-score marking where the ideal or model answer is broken down into specific parts.

Holistic or rating marking in which the answer to a question is not subdivided into specific points and components parts. Thus, the marker makes a single overall judgment of the quality.

Stages or Activities of the Marking Process

The marking process involves several activities which some of these major activities are given below (Hope Journal of Research, 2013):

Pre-Coordination Meeting where the Chief Examiner meets with Assistant Chief Examiners, team leaders and subject specialists to discuss the marking scheme.

Co-ordination Meeting in which case the Chief Examiner with his assistant Chief examiners meets with the whole team of examiners to discuss and finalise the marking scheme (discussion of marking scheme). This is then closely followed by the marking of some standard scripts to ensure fairness to candidates.

Marking that involves markers actually marking the scripts, during which all examiners are carefully checked.

Moderations are done at several stages to ensure that examiners have mastered the marking scheme.

Checking and data input where the marking is checked at the examination board, marks keyed in and statisticians get to work.

Awarding during which papers are scrutinised, archive scripts consulted, standards are discussed and grade boundaries set.

Analysis and data processing where the Board has a huge quantity of data to check, process and print.

In a similar way Ofqual (2013) summarizes the activities of the marking process in nine stages as presented below in Figure 1.

In step 1 the examiners are drilled on how to interpret the marking guide and to identify the symbols used for marking. Step 2 is used to read, correct and amend the marking guide. In step 3 some scripts are read aloud and marked with contributions from all the examiners. Scripts are given out for examiners to mark them individually in step 4. Step 5 involves the checking of examiners' marked scripts by the chief examiners. The marks are filled on the mark sheets in step 6 while the entries are crossed checked in step 7. Step 8 takes care of the grade boundaries while step 9 is the last step during which the results are made known to the public.

Marking Strategies

Greatorex and Suto (2006) proposed a tentative model of marking, which includes five distinct cognitive marking

strategies: matching, scanning, evaluating, scrutinising, and no response.

Matching is a strategy adopted by an examiner when;

“The answer to a question is a visually recognisable item or pattern, for example, a letter or part of a diagram. The examiner looks at a particular location in the answer space and judges whether the candidate’s answer in that space matches the mark scheme answer” (Greatorex and Suto, 2005, p.4).

Scanning has been identified in a number of established and well regarded psychological studies for example Kramer, Coles, and Logan (1996). In essence examiners use it when:

“They survey the whole of the answer space designated to a question to find whether a particular detail in the mark scheme is in the candidate’s answer. This detail could be simple, for example a letter or part of a diagram. Alternatively, it could be more complex, for example, a point in an argument; in such cases, further cognitive marking strategies might also be used” (Greatorex and Suto, 2005, p. 4).

Evaluating as upheld by Greatorex and Suto (2005, p. 4) is identified where an:

“Examiner pays attention to either all or part of the answer space for a question, and the candidate’s answer is processed semantically. The examiner awards marks, bearing in mind the structure, clarity, factual accuracy and logic or other characteristics of the candidate’s answer given in the mark scheme”.

Scrutinising can and does follow on from the above, or is used together with other cognitive strategies but is used only where a response is unpredicted. An examiner:

“Tries to establish whether the candidate has given a valid alternative to the answer in the mark scheme. To do this, the examiner evaluates numerous features of the candidate’s response with the overall aim of reconstructing the candidate’s line of reasoning or establishing what the candidate has attempted to do” (Greatorex and Suto, 2005, p. 4).

No response is a strategy that is self-explanatory. The ‘no response’ strategy is used when a candidate has failed to provide a response to an item (question) in the answer space provided, the examiner looks at the space once or more and then gives 0 mark.

Marking Efficiency

According to Brooks (1980), a substantial minority of

General Certificate of Education (GCE) and Certificate of Secondary Education (CSE) boards was using more than one marker to assess English Language composition scripts completed as part of O-Level or CSE examinations. Matthew (2009) identifies three common errors with examiners: Incorrect adding up of ‘ticks’; transposing the mark given for a question to a mark sheet incorrectly e.g. awarding 5 marks instead of 6; and illegible handwriting.

Suto and Nadas (2008) see that, within the broader educational assessment community, it has long been established that when marking public examinations in the UK, inter-marker agreement is imperfect, varying significantly among examination subjects as well as among teams of markers (Murphy, 1982; Newton and Laming, 2004).

Saddler (2009) argues that the judgments which are made by different Markers about responses of candidates differ. These judgments sometimes depend on who marks the paper. Some of the Markers are generous by their nature, some are strict and some are inconsistent. Some Marker’s judgments are influenced by factors and aspects other than the actual quality of the candidate’s work. These factors include the halo effect, moods, relative effect, personal biases and the amount of effort. Regardless of who marks the script, candidates expect that marks will only be given for the quality of their work.

As viewed by Meadows and Billington (2005), item level marking is more reliable than whole script marking because it reduces the effects of examiner biases. Meadows and Billington found that closely defined questions, which demand definite answers, are associated with higher reliability.

Brooks (2004) on his part says double marking should be targeted at examinations where genuine benefit can be demonstrated. In subjects such as mathematics, where high levels of inter-marker reliability already exist, double-marking would serve little purpose. According to Lucas (1971), there is the need to use as few markers as possible to reduce inter marker variation.

Tisi, Whitehouse, Maughan and Burdett (2013) view that a candidate’s actual score on any particular occasion is made up of their ‘true’ score plus a certain amount of measurement error. On a given day, a candidate might score higher or lower than their true score, depending on how they are feeling, what questions they are asked or who marked the paper. A fair assessment is one in which students are given equitable opportunities to demonstrate what they know (Lam, 1995). Each year individual students are given the wrong marks and grades, for reasons that vary annually, are unpredictable, too often remain unexplained and significantly undermine the confidence of teachers in all schools and colleges. And each year redress remains costly and difficult for hard-pressed schools to secure.

Minimising Subjectivity

Subjective marking is marking in which the marks awarded depend on the personal opinion or condition of the Marker instead of the marking guidelines. (Mthembu 2014). The hand book “Learning to Teach, Teaching to Learn. 2014: 2” reveals four causes of subjectivity:

Halo Effect

In the marking and assessment context, the “halo effect” refers to the cognitive biases of Markers that attend to their thinking causing them to apply their overall impression of the candidate, their likeability and their successfulness (Learning to Teach, Teaching to Learn, 2014). The “halo effect” can be a challenge in the marking of public examinations in the following ways: A candidate can answer the first two parts of the question very well and the Marker can end up assuming that the following questions are good and give a wrong grade. The opposite can happen when the candidate has answered the first two questions of a section in a dismally poor manner and then the Marker assumes that the candidate is generally a poor learner. This is likely to influence the grading of the rest of the candidates questions. The Chief markers can decide start with the distribution of full time candidates’ scripts because they write all the subjects. After the completion of full time candidates, the Chief marker then releases the scripts of part-time candidates because they are fewer. If Markers happen to know about this arrangement (that the coming consignment is of part-time candidates), they may be influenced by the “halo effect” and grade them lower because of the myth that part-time candidates are poor performers.

Relative Effect

The relative effect refers to the influence of the work of one candidate in the scoring of another candidate. This happens when the Marker first reads the responses of a good candidate, score him/her a good grade. When the same Marker reads a response of the average candidate who is not as good as the first one, he/she gives a lower score because the responses do not come anywhere closer those of the previous candidate. This often happens when Markers read essay questions or long paragraph responses (Learning to Teach, Teaching to Learn, 2014). The problem with relative effect is that the decision of the Marker is influenced by the performance of the first group of candidates and not by the guidelines in the memorandum.

Personal Biases

Personal biases are the tendencies of Markers to use their own personal beliefs to make decisions about a candidate’s responses. This often happens when Markers deal with questions which require an opinion of the candidate about a particular idea or a process or a decision or a form of behavior. The influence of personal biases happens when the Marker becomes more indulgent towards an answer that adopts a view that is similar to his/her personal view. Personal biases are very dangerous especially in questions where the candidates are expected to raise their viewpoint about particular issues from the source material (e.g. a cartoon or a newspaper extract). If this happens a Marker may be unconsciously tempted to give higher marks to candidates who argue in favour of a view which is not similar to his or her own personal view (Learning to Teach, Teaching to Learn, 2014).

Moods / Physical State and Emotional State

The marking of the National Senior Certificate examination is a taxing excessive both emotionally and physically. The Markers must complete the assessment of thousands of candidates within a short period of time. The Marker must mark the work which was completed in more than eight months in a matter of less than 20 days. This kind of work needs reading, decision making, consistency and accuracy. All these demands of the marking task are likely to affect the marking process. The effect of moods and physical state can be seen during the appeals process where more errors are identified in the scripts which are marked towards the end of the marking day or towards the end of the marking period. Since marking is taxing physically and mentally, Markers must not mark when tired or hungry. This affects the quality of marking. It is therefore important that Markers eat on time and work for a reasonable number of hours. The problem of emotions is usually evident towards the end of marking when Markers try to mark faster to complete and go home (Learning to Teach, Teaching to Learn, 2014). Chief Markers must manage the final days of marking in such a way that the last candidates to be marked are not unfairly disadvantaged.

Gender and Marking Reliability

The marking of public examinations tends to be a male dominated pursuit (Greatorex & Bell, (2004). They also found that there was no discernable relationship between gender and marking reliability. Hamp-Lyons (1990) holds that examiner behaviour varies with different groups, such as professional background, subject specialization

and gender. In all, Greateorex and Bell (2004, p.11) summarize that:

“As a general rule the sex and gender of examiners and interactions between candidate’s sex and examiner sex does not affect the marks that candidates gain at the unit level. In other words although examining is male dominated this has not resulted in a bias against girls or boys in the marking”.

They did however feel that as good practice, based on the findings of their study and those discussed above, gender bias in marking is something which should be monitored but that it was unlikely to be significant enough to affect overall grades.

Validity and Consistency of Marking

Validity of Marking

This is one of the most important aspects of quality marking. Markers must differentiate between the assessments of content of the candidate’s answer from the assessment of the candidate’s writing style. A Marker must not focus on language expression and language competency except in cases where the medium is the message. Exclude as far as possible interferences from such distractions as poor handwriting and untidiness. (Learning to Teach, Teaching to Learn, 2014).

Consistency of Marking

The style of marking is also an important factor that influences the consistency of marking. There is an argument that intra consistency should be considered the more important of the two as without internal consistency over a series of scripts the marks assigned will be haphazard and unjustifiable and no form of moderation or adjustment of marks will be able to resolve this. In a practical sense this can result in an entire batch of scripts marked by an examiner having to be remarked on because a mark adjustment cannot accurately be made e.g. + 4 marks. That some of the scripts will warrant the extra 4 marks, whereas others will not. This is explored further by Thyne (1974) who reasoned that although marking-consistency is necessary for maximum validity; *other* conditions also need to be fulfilled. The “whole script marking” model must be the last choice that the Chief Marker must think of. The following are factors which favour the “marking per question” model:

Markers get used to the memorandum faster than it would have been with the whole script.

Marking flows faster without compromising accuracy.

The flow of completed scripts is not retarded by long time taken to mark the entire Script.

New Markers can be given shorter questions until they are accurate and confident.

The moderation of scripts by the Senior Markers becomes easier than in the marking of the entire scripts.

It is easy to assess consistency of marking as the Senior Marker deals with a group that marks one question.

The pace of marking helps the Chief Marker to identify popular and unpopular questions and to reorganize the marking team where necessary.

Going through the entire script necessitates keeping a greater range of answers in mind which complicates the judgments as marking continues. (Learning to Teach, Teaching to Learn, 2014).

Theoretical Review

Goal setting Theory

The historical origin of this theory dates to the early twentieth century, but Locke and Latham (1990) are recognized for the development of this theory (Mbua 2003). The theory posits that goals are the most important factors affecting the motivation and behaviour of employees. Thus the theory emphasizes the importance of specific and challenging goals in achieving motivated behaviour. Specific goals often involve quantitative targets for improvement in behaviour of interest. Research indicates that specific performance goals are much more effective and motivational than vague goals in which a person is told to “do your best”.

Goal commitment and self-efficacy are important factors of the goal setting theory. Goal commitment means the more dedicated an individual is to achieving the goal, the more he/she is motivated to accomplish the goal. Research also holds that having employees participate in goal setting will increase their level of goal commitment. Self-efficacy is the individual’s belief that he/she can successfully complete a particular task; thereby increasing motivation.

Based on this theory, GCE examiners can develop self-efficacy by improving their professional status through professional training and seminars/workshops. This therefore keeps the examiners better prepared and motivated for efficient marking.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive survey research design. This is an approach of descriptive research that blends quantitative and qualitative data to provide

relevant and accurate information. It is a time-effect research method and it engages people who are at the centre of the research objective. Surveys are used to gather data from a sample of a population at a particular time.

Area of Study

This study was conducted in the Republic of Cameroon. It involved all GCE examiners for the general subjects in the whole territory of the country Cameroon. GCE examiners are usually selected by the Cameroon GCE Board from public, denominational and lay private institutions. A good number of examiners also come from the Ministry and Delegations of Secondary Education as well as some University lecturers within Cameroon. Geographically, the Republic of Cameroon is located between latitudes 20 North to 140 North of the equator and latitudes 80 East to 170 East of the Greenwich meridian. Cameroon has boundaries to the North with the Republic of Chad, to the West with the Federal Republic of Nigeria, to the East with the Central African Republic and to the South with Equatorial Guinea, Congo and the Atlantic Ocean. The two official languages of the country are English and French.

Population of the Study

The target population of this study was made up of all the GCE examiners and chief examiners of the General Education subjects since the inception of the Cameroon GCE Board. The accessible population was made up of all the GCE examiners and Chief Examiners of the general education subjects for the 2021 marking session. This made up 3641 Ordinary Level and 1694 Advanced Level examiners giving a total of 5335 examiners. There were 18 Ordinary Level and 18 Advanced Level chief examiners, making a total of 36 chief examiners. From the above accessible population a sample of 360 examiners and all the 36 chief examiners was selected.

Sampling Technique

The simple random sampling technique was used to select examiners. This technique avoids bias as it gives every member of the accessible population an equal chance of taking part in the study. It also enables the researcher to get diverse responses over his findings. All the chief examiners were purposively selected as samples, given that there is usually just one chief examiner per subject.

Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument used for this study was the Likert scale questionnaire. There were two sets of questionnaire, one for GCE examiners and another for GCE chief examiners. The questionnaire for GCE examiners was made up of two parts. Part I was made up of background information, while part II was made up of two sections A and B. Section A had five structured or closed ended items to elicit quantitative information about examiners' professional status, while section B was composed of two open ended items aimed at finding out measures that could be taken to improve the efficiency of GCE marking. The questionnaire for GCE chief examiners also had background information that was followed by one section with five items aimed at getting information about the marking efficiencies of GCE examiners.

Validity of Instrument

The researcher carried out both content and face validation to ensure that the instruments were good enough for the study. After constructing the two sets of questionnaire, the researcher presented them to his peers and then to the supervisor for any necessary adjustments. The researcher then carried out a pilot study where he administered some of the questionnaire to GCE examiners of technical subjects who did not form part of his target population, to ensure that the constructs were all understood.

Reliability of Instrument

The researcher further carried out a reliability analysis on both questionnaire for examiners and chief examiners. The results indicated that both questionnaire were reliable with Crombach's alpha reliability coefficients of 0.79 for examiners' questionnaire and 0.73 for chief examiners' questionnaire.

Administration of Instrument

Questionnaire were administered to the GCE examiners and chief examiners during the marking of the June 2021 session of the GCE that took place in Buea and Limbe. While the researcher was at the Buea marking centre, one of his colleagues assisted him to administer questionnaire to the examiners who were at the Limbe marking centre. All questionnaire issued out were collected back at the spot giving a 100% return rate.

Table 1. Perceived Professional Status of Examiners

Professional status and GCE Marking	Agree	Disagree	No idea	N
Experienced teachers show better mastery of the assessment or marking process.	334(82.8%)	25(6.9%)	1(0.3%)	360
An understanding of the Bloom's taxonomy makes one a better examiner.	313(86.9%)	44(12.2%)	3(0.8%)	360
I am usually troubled by candidates' bad hand writing.	332(92.2%)	28(7.8%)	0(0.0%)	360
Inconsistent examiners are most often replaced.	273(75.8%)	59(16.4%)	28(7.8%)	360
A professional examiner is more reliable than a non-professional.	301(83.6%)	51(14.2%)	8(2.2%)	360
Multiple respond set (MRS)	1553(86.3%)	207(11.5%)	40(2.2%)	1800

Table 2. Distribution of professional status of examiners by background indicators

Background information	Category	Perceived professional status (Aggregated score using MRS and n _{responses})			χ ² -test
		Agree	Disagree	No Idea	
Type of institution	Public	1220(86.5%)	158(11.2%)	32(2.3%)	χ ² =0.670 p=0.717
	Denominational	251(86.6%)	32(11.0%)	7(2.4%)	
	Lay private	82(82.0%)	17(17.0%)	1(1.0%)	
Gender	Male	897(87.1%)	116(11.3%)	17(1.7%)	χ ² =0.25 p=0.620
	Female	656(85.2%)	91(11.8%)	23(3.0%)	
Type of certificate	Education related certificate	514(44.7%)	526(45.8%)	109(9.5%)	χ ² =0.55 p=0.457
	Non education related certificate	232(40.6%)	272(47.6%)	68(11.9%)	
Teaching experience categorized	≤5 years	35(87.5%)	4(10.0%)	1(2.5%)	χ ² =0.37 p=0.830
	6-10 years	350(84.3%)	50(12.0%)	15(3.6%)	
	11+ years	1168(86.8%)	153(11.4%)	24(1.8%)	
Marking experience categorized	≤5 years	456(83.7%)	69(12.7%)	20(3.7%)	χ ² =1.13 p=0.570
	6-10 years	558(87.2%)	73(11.4%)	9(1.4%)	
	11+ years	539(87.6%)	65(10.6%)	11(1.8%)	

FINDINGS

The data gathered for this research were in both quantitative and qualitative. Open-ended questions were analyzed using the process of thematic analysis. Data were made essentially of categorical variables and were analyzed using frequencies, proportions and Multiple Responses Analysis. Chi-Square test of independence was used to measure the association between the conceptual indicators and background information such as sex, age, qualification and experience. The non-parametric Spearman's rho correlation test was then used to measure the relationship between conceptual components and the dependent variable (aimed at assessing examiners' efficiency of marking the GCE). Data were presented using statistical tables and code-quotation grounding tables. All statistics were presented at the 95% confidence level (CL), Alpha =0.05 (Nana, 2012). The results of the analysis are presented on Table1.

It was agreed by the greater majority of examiners that professional status influences GCE marking (86.3%).

This trend was still very high for all the indicators of this component therefore indicating that professional status significantly impacts GCE marking (table 1). The perception of the GCE examiners in relation to this indicator did not differ significantly with sex, type of institution, teaching and marking experience or type of certificate, thus implying that they were really unanimous that professional status has a lot to play in GCE marking (P>0.05), as shown on table 2.

Hypothesis Testing

There is no significant relationship between examiners' academic status and GCE marking efficiency.

The results of this hypothesis testing is shown on table 3.

There was statistically enough evidence that professional status impacts GCE marking efficiency (R=0.166; P=0.001), table 3. In general, the better the professional status, the better the marking efficiency. In view of this therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis retained.

Table 3. Relationship between Professional Status and Marking Efficiency

Professional status	Marking efficiency	
	Correlation Coefficient	.166**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
N	360	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 2. Chief Examiners' Perception on Examiners' Efficiency

Perception of GCE Chief Examiners

The perception of GCE chief examiners on examiners' efficiency is presented below on figure 2.

It was generally revealed that some examiners make counting errors when summing up the marks of candidates 35 (97.2%), that some examiners usually have mark differences of about five and above when checked by the chiefs 31 (86.1%), that some examiners usually mark below the number of scripts allocated for each examiner by the Cameroon General Certificate of Examination Board 26 (72.2%). To some greater extent Chief Examiners were of the opinion that some examiners only prepare their own marking guides on the first day of the marking session 22 (61.1%) and less than the majority 17 (47.2%) agreed that all examiners usually

come to the marking center with their own prepared marking guides as expected.

Qualitative Analysis

These are presented on table 4 below. GCE markers sampled for this study suggested what could be done to improve the efficiency of GCE marking. Most of the sampled GCE markers suggested an increase in the number of days for the marking exercise or better still increase in the number of markers for the exercise. Other markers recommended that the marking centers should be more conducive with good chairs, toilets, lighting and accessibility. A handful of examiners said the GCE Board should organize training seminars and colloquiums for

Table 4. Thematic Analysis Depicting Examiners' Suggestions to Improve Efficiency of GCE marking

Code	Code description	n	Quotation
Working environment	Conducive marking centers (chair, lighting, toilets, water, hygiene, accessibility)	49	'the marking accommodation centers should be comfortable' 'Good marking environment, good chairs, benches, good lighting system and toilets' 'Comfortable marking environment and halls'
Financial motivation	Increase script due	66	'Should increase transport' 'Outstation allowance should be increased' 'Increase out station allowances taking into consideration experience, number of years put in as teacher in a private school.'
On the spot payments	Out station allowance payment	45	'Paying the out station allowance before marking exercise begins' 'Outstation allowance should be paid immediately after the marking exercise'
Disclose performance	Disclosing marking performance or grade of examiners, rewarding best markers	6	'Make the grade known to examiners' 'If best markers are financially motivated or recognized'
Duration	Increase number of marking days or reducing number of script or increase number of examiners	83	'Examiners should not be compelled to mark at least 200 scripts over the period' 'Number of scripts marked per day should be reduced' 'Increase markers' 'French and English should be considered as difficult scripts to mark, thus more days allocated'
Scripts sharing	Initial sharing of all scripts from day one as opposed to the current finish and take.	22	'Each examiner should be given the total number of script to mark at once so that they should not hurry.'
Encourage specialization	Assigning script based on specialization	11	'Encouraging specialization'
Selection of examiners	competence, no favoritism, replacing aging examiners	39	'Only those who teach should be invited to mark' 'A hitch-free selection of markers and less bias' 'All fraud should be stop at all level, 'Aging examiners should be replaced'
Capacity building	Capacity building through seminars and colloquium by the GCE board	14	'GCE Board should organized seminars and colloquium. Teachers should be drilled on assessment criteria'. 'Training as to enable mastering of scheme of the marking guide'
More chiefs	Increasing the number of chiefs examiners	1	'Many more chiefs to check the scripts'

N=290

examiners. Teachers should be drilled on assessment criteria. A good number believed that assigning scripts based on specialization and not favoritism, and replacing aging examiners will improve the efficiency of GCE marking. The initial sharing of all scripts from day one as opposed to the current finish and take system could certainly improve on the efficiency of GCE marking as perceived by many of them.

A good portion of the sampled GCE markers however emphasized on payment of out station allowances within the marking period. Many suggested that disclosing the marking performance (grades) of examiners and rewarding best markers is a preferable way of improving efficiency of GCE marking.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the findings of this study a greater majority of the respondents agreed that professional status has an influence on an examiners' marking efficiency. Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis retained.

This view is supported by Lewis (1974) who says inter testing reliability for individual administered tests can be increased by restricting the selection of testers to trained persons, all of whom follow a standardised procedure. Ruth and Murphy (1988) and Weigle (1998) indicate that training is fundamental in stabilizing marking agreements across faculty members. Mthembu (2014) views training

as very important in the professionalism of examiners when he says various factors have been identified by various scholars as likely to contribute to the accuracy of marking. These factors include the general knowledge and the level of education of the marker, subject knowledge, personality and work ethics, teaching and marking experience as well as training provided.

Nootboom (2006) also holds that the theories on trust show the importance of competence, integrity and dedication of the members of a profession to gain the trust of the public and the state and to justify the professional mandate. All these go a long way to justify the importance of professionalism or training on efficient marking.

CONCLUSION

This study was aimed at investigating the effects of examiners' professional status on the efficiency of marking GCE examinations. It was revealed that professional status is a very important determinant of the efficiency of marking examinations such as the GCE. Considering the dangers of the examination marking crisis on certificate recognition, this research saw professional training before marking as an important tool for achieving marking efficiency. Although an examiner's marking ability is also determined by accuracy, consistency, fairness, effectiveness and others, efficiency (a function of how effective the marking is done with time) stands as a better measuring rod, since it engulfs the other determinants.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of this study the following suggestions were made:

1. The GCE board could organize regular seminar/workshops either directly or through the use of trainers to train both GCE examiners and would be examiners on GCE marking.
2. The Conveyor Belt marking system should be applied during marking, where several examiners successively mark a script with each examiner marking only a particular question(s) or section(s). This encourages specialization.
3. Two independent marking of all scripts if not at least for the scripts with borderline scores (39-49 for O/L and 34-44 for A/L) could also increase marking efficiency.
4. The selection of examiners should be strictly based on professional backings.
5. Chief and assistant chief examiners could share to each examiner his/her total stipulated number of scripts for the whole session from day one to avoid unnecessary rush.

6. GCE examiners should be more committed and responsible especially during the marking exercise.

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